

**Recent Trends, Challenges, and Approaches to ELT: Digi-Teachers as a Need of the 21st
Century**

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Abstract

The world has transformed into a digital space that now fits into the palm of every hand. The overwhelming amount of available information often gives the impression that it can replace the teacher. Teaching and learning practices have advanced alongside technological developments. The older model of teaching—restricted to classrooms and lecture halls—has shifted into blended learning environments. The Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) approach has now taken the lead, replacing many theories from previous decades of language learning.

Teachers and institutional administrators face various challenges. They not only need to be experts in their subject area but must also possess technological literacy to provide rich and innovative learning experiences for students. However, not every school or college has sufficient funding to equip their centers with modern technologies or multimedia tools, nor does every student have access to all necessary facilities. Therefore, teachers need to become Digi-Teachers and continuously upskill themselves. Globally connected teachers can overcome many challenges by sharing useful insights, resources, and techniques with one another.

This paper aims to explore the ways teachers can develop their expertise by effectively using technology and online resources, as well as the hurdles and barriers they may encounter when implementing this knowledge in underprivileged or resource-limited areas.

Keywords: ICT, CALL/CALT, teacher development, Digi-Teacher, global community, CLT approach, challenges and solutions

Recent Trends, Challenges and Approaches to ELT

The youth maker, the generation builder and often said the future builder of any nation are the teachers, on whom the parents and the nation entrust for their heir's success and life achievements. The teacher must be competent, proficient, qualified and skilled to deliver the same level of expertise to his disciples.

Educators are lifelong learners. No one could meet that pinnacle of acquisition where he does not need to elevate or enhance his skills set further. Revolutionary discoveries and innovations are recorded every day throughout the world in this age of technology.

Anybody who has lived in the past two decades witnesses the rapid change and advancement in every discipline of life. Advancement of technology impacted the educational system too and the pandemic (COVID) spurred it to reach the upmost potential.

Background of the study:

The world is closely knitted through the internet and latest technologies. People around the world benefit in every field of life. Some institutes and teachers use modern technologies to upskill and reskill their students to meet the prevalent, current level of qualification. The ELT trends, methodologies and approaches have been changed to make the teaching and learning process effective and enjoyable. However, there are many who are lagging behind. Specifically, in English language teaching and learning and the use of latest technologies.

Purpose of the study:

The purpose of the study is to find out the perceptions and views of teachers about the use of latest technologies in teaching and learning English language. Its goal to raise awareness to teach English for the global perspective rather than the individual needs.

The paper also aims at finding difficulties and barriers in using the advance technologies and approaches in teaching English language and provides some useful insights of certain development programs for teachers and digital learning platforms to upskill themselves as a solution.

The paper emphasizes the need for globally connected teachers and learners via technology.

Global Perspective:

A recent shift is seen in ELT is from “TENOR (teaching English for no obvious reasons) by TESR (teaching English for social responsibilities)” (Tesol International Association). It is the part of the past when teachers do not know why to teach English and they just adhere to the literature, grammar and core syllabus for the year.

A growing number of educators are now beginning to discuss what the aims of English language teaching should be, given the serious global issues that face our world. Other educators prefer to talk about the moral dimension of English teaching and the need for an approach to language education which aims at fostering a sense of social responsibility in students. The implication here is that we can't call our English teaching successful if our students, however fluent, are ignorant of world problems, have no social conscience or use their communication skills for international crime, exploitation, oppression or environmental destruction. (Cates, 1997)

International issues as a content of Language Teaching:

Apart from English literature and stories, that contains almost fictions and donot arouse critical thinking and problem solving in learners, the recent trend shifts towards factual, current national, international and environmental issuses.It is the part of the theory, that yarn to evoke humanity and inclusion in young learners.

The key features of ELT content include acceptance of other cultures, customs and religions. It raises awareness about global environmental issues.

Role of Teacher:

21st century put heavy responsibilities on teachers' shoulders besides mere imparting the core subject knowledge.It does not only burdenize the teachers to make students realize and understands about global issues but to develop interpersonal skills among them.By connecting to the global community, teachers can get their students connected with the the other part of the world's learner, may be different in language, culture or having contrasting values and mindset.

Teacher can inculcate the positive behaviour in learners while using the technology to share the area of expertise and knowledge with the fellow of other country. It may broaden the vision of the diverse group of intellectuals, race, gender, language or religion, when they meet each other with open hearts and open mind. The students across the world will learn to accept, respect and befriend of different beliefs.They will learn to meet on a common ground. This may bring a change in the world's rigid mindset and can make the world a better place for the people.

21st Century Learning Design (21CLD):

To live and work in the 21st century successfully, students must develop a range of skills and competencies on top of mere core subject knowledge. Their learning does not end in graduation. They need to learn and gain new skills throughout their career.

21st century learners need skills to manage and analyze information, think critically, innovate, communicate clearly, collaborate and build relationships.

Interpersonal skills are of greater importance in the 21st century than they were ever before. Learners only gain these skills by doing. Memorizing and repeating information for reports and tests does not develop these skills. As educators, it's our responsibility to create learning activities that allow learners to practice these skills.

Communicative Competence:

Translation Methods, Audio lingual methods and Direct methods, however, are used in many countries for EFL learners, nevertheless, the recent approach to teaching English Language is the communicative language teaching (CLT) approach. It is an approach to language teaching and learning that involves knowledge of the language itself. It emphasizes meaningful communication according to social and cultural rules and makes learners practice the use of language change depending on the context.

It focusses on fluency rather than accuracy. However, great deals of activities are also done for getting accuracy.

Digi Teacher:

Use of You Tube videos and PowerPoint presentations have become common in various settings of classroom. Pandemic COVID 19 spread the revolution of latest technologies across the world. Google classroom, LMS, Zoom, Google Meet and WhatsApp groups for Education purpose faced massive growth around the globe.

E- learning changed the flavor of teaching. The multitude of institutes start using smart board in their physical classrooms too. Teachers remain in touch with students 24/7 through

WhatsApp group, more commonly. Students are also facilitated to ask any query however; they are at homes too.

Latest Technologies and Apps in ELT:

Numerous Apps and websites are there to accelerate the English Language Learning and Teaching. You Tube, social media are filled to overflowing with teaching and learning materials. Mobile learning and Gamification are common. Wordable, Essential English, Duolingo, BBC, Wordsearch, language lab is also in practice. Link online learners is the best example of inclusion and wellbeing.

Escape the Classroom (Perceptia Press, UK/Japan) for example, requires students to work together in teams to figure out ways of solving puzzles and breaking codes to escape a room. The approach that Fun Skills (CUP and Cambridge Assessment English, UK) takes to this is perhaps reflected in its title, as children prepare for the exams they need to take in the future through songs and entertaining stories. (British Council)

Barriers:

Division of Technology

Latest Technology is not reachable to everyone. The reason is the socio-economic states of many people regardless of developed or developing countries or cities. There are many regions in a developed country and some districts in a cosmopolitan city where the masses do not have access to somewhat i-e called technology. They even do not aware of the blessings they might have. It is the greatest barrier in teaching and learning process.

A digital divide can also exist between schools within a single area or city. (Warschauer et al., 2004), as well as within classrooms, depending on whether learners have access to technology at home or not, and how technology is used in the home – for example, whether primarily for entertainment and shopping rather than for family learning (Grant, 2009)

In Canada, a high resource context, a study examining the inequal cities in internet access and use of social networks found a clear digital divide between individuals with lower or higher levels of income and education, as well as between rural and urban communities, between older and younger internet users, and between immigrants and Canadian born residents (Haight et al., 2014). Hixon and Buckenmeyer (2009) state that it was widely believed among policymakers and school administrators that giving technology in the hands of students and teachers would instantly result in effective use of technologies (Hixon & Buckenmeyer, 2009). While it is essential to have technology to be able to integrate it into the system, it is also important to realize that the mere abundant existence of technology in schools will not solely improve teaching practices and earning outcomes (Berrett et al, 2012; Hixon & Buckenmeyer,)

Socio-Economical states:

Pakistan had a population of 223.0 million in January 2021. 37.3% of Pakistan's population lives in urban centers, while 62.7% lives in rural areas. Internet penetration in Pakistan stood at 27.5% in January 2021. The number of social media users in Pakistan was equivalent to 20.6% of the total population in January 2021. (datareportal)

Karachi, a metropolitan city, does not have a populace with equal distribution of facilities and technology. Some institutes in aristocratic areas do have the recent advanced technologies and approaches to teaching while in contrast, the zone with lower socio economics level have the lower resources and awareness about revolutionary world.

The lower social and economic condition of any region is also a ground of lower technological resources and awareness.

Academic Heads:

In most of the schools and universities, teachers and lecturers are the employees of the institutes. They are assigned to complete a certain syllabus in certain periods of time. Teachers are not free to choose or design the syllabus according to the need of their students. Therefore, they do not take pains to upskill or reskill themselves.

The role of academic heads is of great importance as he is the authority figure who can implement the latest trends, approaches and technologies in his institute.

Recommendations

We live in an age of tremendous opportunity. We have prepared free lesson plans and resources to apply in our classrooms. There are many websites such as Oxford ELT, American English for educators, Cambridge and British council who provides free development programs to teachers across the world.

Oxford ELT:

It provides hundreds of Teachings and learning resources. Oxford Teachers Club is a community of 1.2 million members. One can receive ESL news and resources direct to his inbox. In addition, it provides over 20,000 free lesson plans, worksheets, and activities, and unlimited access to the webinar library. (Oxford)

British council Connecting Classroom:

British council Connecting Classroom is a global-facing program which connected schools across 40 countries, focused on the development of core skills alongside subject knowledge. It did this through training and connecting teachers, facilitating learning in a range of different international contexts, and engaging policymakers to extend their understanding of effective practice internationally and support their education policy development aspirations. Teachers also accessed a range of classroom resources, including projects based on the Sustainable Development Goals, helping young people develop core skills and explore important global themes. (British Council)

Microsoft Education:

Microsoft Education offers free professional development, training and collaboration to build teachers' capacity. It believes on being a part of the education community globally, one can do amazing things. Education centers offer student -centered learning, STEM coding and

e-sports and many more. 21CLD supports educators to develop the 21st century essential skills in young learners.

ME (Microsoft Educator) Trainer is designed to provide you with a solid foundation on the range of Microsoft technologies and resources that support student-centered learning. These are based on authentic problems and projects and align to 21st Century Skills, ISTE standards for students, and UNESCO's ICT Framework for teachers. (Microsoft Education)

Artificial Intelligence:

The great gift of the 21st century is AI. AI has a massive impact on education. Not only can students use AI for writing their assignments, but teachers can also create their lesson plans and handbooks. ChatGPT became a threat for educators, however, the researchers at Stanford University have created a tool called DetectGPT (ProPakistani) to help teachers identify content generated by ChatGPT and other similar large language models. (LLMs).

We can use Storywizard.AI to produce short, illustrated stories within minutes. Character.AI is an interesting website to chat with any character from history or present. It is good for fun and learning together. Chatbot is not only for written assignments but can be used for enhancing communication skills.

We are living in an age of tremendous opportunity. We have a bundle of resources and materials just a click away. Upskill, reskill, training or development does not remain an unsolved problem. The promising future of our generation is in our hands. We can do it together by joining hands: Government officials, policy makers, academic heads and teachers from around the globe can do it together. We can change the world with malice towards none and charity

towards all, with changing the minds of the future of tomorrow. Can we not take a step further for a better tomorrow?

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